

Psychological features of students' educational stresses

Marqarita Soqrina

Minsk, Kiev State University, Ukraine

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Abstract: For some, student life is usually associated with student societies, communication with interested people, various events and celebrations. For others, it is remembered as a serious test, lifestyle changes, difficult living conditions to get used to. Students face various problems at a young age, the new educational environment requires them to be more self-confident, responsible, disciplined, and not all students are able to cope with this. In any case, going to college --- means stress to many students. The student must overcome obstacles, assume new roles and adapt to the new situation by changing the old ones.

Introduction

There are many opinions that chronic stress is a constant companion for students. According to researchers, the causes of stress in students are mainly related to finances, housing, security and so on. We can also say that the stress experienced by students hinders their academic success. This failure, in turn, causes discomfort, which in turn increases the overall stress.

Study of stress.

Hypothesis: It can be considered that increasing the workload during the educational process is one of the main causes of stress. In this case, we will solve the following tasks:

1. To analyze the psychological and pedagogical literature and determine the meaning of the concepts "stress", "stress in student life", "main features of youth".
2. To study the psychological characteristics of educational stress in students.
3. To study the psychological characteristics of stress in students.

In this case, the following psychodiagnostic methods will be used.

Test on educational stress (developed by YV Sherbatykh YV Sherbatykh).

Stress Tolerance Assessment Test (developed by Kouchen and Willison).

Part 1. Theoretical analysis of the psychological characteristics of educational stress in students during higher education.

The essence of the concept of "stress"

One of the most common affective conditions today is stress. Stress refers to an extremely strong and long-lasting psychological stress, during which the nervous system is subjected to emotional stress. Stress disrupts a person's activity and interferes with the normal course of his behavior. If stress occurs

frequently and for a long time, it affects not only the psychological but also the physical condition. Severe physical disorders, such as cardiovascular and digestive system diseases, occur as a result of stress.

Translated from the English language, the word stress means pressure, tension, as well as external influences. The concept of stress is gradually entering our lives. In 1936, Canadian physician and biologist G. Selye defined stress as a specific response to any student encountered.

There are different approaches to stress in psychology.

Stress is the body's response to non-specific effects that disrupt its physical and psychological state, as well as the corresponding state of the body's nervous system. A non-specific reaction means that a living organism always responds with the same physiological change reactions to the general adaptive symptoms of any student it encounters. The body's non-specific response to various harmful effects is called general adaptation syndrome or stress. This is Selye's definition of stress.

Stress is also considered an indicator of an individual's physiological, psychological and behavioral levels in extreme situations. Extreme conditions are extremely strong environmental impacts that reach unbearable levels and can lead to disruption of the adaptation mechanism. Extreme factors lead to certain changes in the body. In this case, physical, physico-chemical and socio-psychological factors play a role.

Another name for stress is defined as a situation in which a person is extremely tense.

They determine the basis for the stressors that affect the types of stress. Stressors are various extreme effects that lead to an undesirable functional condition - stress.

a) Physiological stressors --- extreme physical exertion, low or high temperature, pain stimuli, etc.

b) Psychological stressors --- factors of signal importance, danger, threat, information loading, etc.

Researchers identify two forms of stress: positive stress — eustress and harmful stress — distress. In many cases, stress refers to the negative effects of the environment or external influences.

Certain conditions are required for stress to be eustress: a positive emotional background, experience in solving such problems and positive forecasts for the future, appreciation of the individual's actions by the social environment, having sufficient resources to prevent stress. The absence of these factors is necessary for the transformation of stress into distress, but also other factors of objective and subjective nature are required: emotional-cognitive factors: lack of necessary information, negative prognosis, helplessness in the face of the problem, etc. overcoming adaptability, longevity, etc.

It should be noted that stress is a difficult, ambiguous concept, and stress manifests itself at various levels of the existence of a biosocial being called man. Everyone, regardless of age, gender and socio-demographic situation, faces stress. That is why we often face stress.

Gubachev, Yu.M., Ievlev, BV, Karvasarsky, B.D. and others. Emotional stress in the conditions of norms and pathology [Text] : L. : Medicine , 1996. - 224 p . --- Emotional stress in normal and pathological conditions, 1996 , Medicine , p.224

The extent to which stressors affect our bodies can vary, ranging from mild depression to post-traumatic stress disorder to post-traumatic psychosomatic disorders. Stress in all cases affects all components of our individuality, memory, consciousness, speech, emotional-volitional sphere. However, this does not mean that stress is bad, unpleasant, stress is also an important training procedure for strengthening a person, it is important to increase the resistance of the psyche and the body in general. Stress is an important ally of ours in terms of adapting to any changes in the environment.

For most people, some symptoms of stress are identified:

Inability to concentrate on work ;

Fast - fast to begin _ pages ; _

Memory impairment;

Constant fatigue;

Unnaturally fast or slow speech ;

Frequent headaches, pains of the digestive system caused by organic causes;

Anxiety and nervousness;

Increased bad habits;

Loss of sense of humor;

Constant hunger or loss of this feeling .

These symptoms may occur separately, however These symptoms can also be the result of serious problems, nervous tension and reduced ability to work.

Individual-typical features of the nervous system and personality play an important role in the correction of a person's mental state during stress, in response to environmental stressors. . Also, people who love life are stronger, they do not lose control in difficult situations.

The difference in human self-esteem manifests itself in such cases, where people with lower self-esteem feel greater fear in difficult situations created by the environment. They think they are not strong enough to fix the situation, so they move with less energy, try to adapt to the situation, and tend to avoid difficulties because they do not believe they can fix the situation. It turns out that stress exists to a large extent as an individual phenomenon.

Игумнов, С.А. Stress management: modern psychological and medical approaches [Text] : SPb: Rech, 2007. - 217 p. Stress management: modern psychological and pharmacological methods, Rech, 2007, p.217

In order to help a person in such cases, it is necessary to teach him certain tricks, to instill in him the habits of behavior in stressful situations. It is also necessary to increase self-confidence.

Numerous studies by Selye and others show that unpredictable and unmanageable events are more dangerous than predictable and manageable situations. When people know how things are going, they can influence them, at

least in part, to protect themselves from unpleasant situations. At the same time, the probability of stress is significantly reduced.

Possible reactions of the body to stress:

By reacting to stress, a person deliberately or subconsciously tries to adapt to a new situation. Then comes the stage of balancing or adapting the situation. The person either adapts to the situation and the stress does not produce any negative results, or he is unable to adapt, and a condition called bad adaptation occurs. As a result, various mental and physical deviations can occur. Passivity occurs in people with low adaptive reserves and inability to withstand stress. At this time, helplessness, despair, depression arise. However, such a stress reaction can be temporary.

The other two reactions are active and subject to human will. Active protection from stress occurs when a person changes his sphere of activity and finds something more suitable and useful for moral balance. Active relaxation increases the natural adaptability of the human body, both physically and mentally. This is considered a more natural reaction.

In this sense, stress is a specific reaction of a person to mental and physical stresses, which are considered physiological reflexes. Stress is a part of our lives. Stress is with us all day long, it affects our every move. Stress can be both beneficial and destructive: beneficial stress provides energy, and destructive stress manifests itself in the form of headaches, hypertension, stomach ulcers, chronic insomnia and others.

1.2. Features of stress in student life. Student life is full of extraordinary and stressful processes, so students often experience stress and neuropsychological tension. The main stress in students is caused by a large flow of information, lack of systematic work during the semester, stress during the sessions. Emotional tension in students begins 3-4 days before the session and continues throughout the session on the quietest days. This type of stress can lead to neurosis, functional disorders of the nervous system, in which case the nervous system is damaged in the first place, depleting its resources by forcing the body to work under constant stress. Neurosis is not a disease, but a variety of "normal" reactions under unusual stress conditions. In turn, stress is caused by arguments, failures in life and other situations, which psychiatrists consider as mental traumas. The duration of education has a significant impact on the formation of a person's personality, so the problem of mental health of students is very relevant.

Researchers divide students into 3 groups: Group 1 --- those with neurotic disorders Group 2 --- those at risk of such disorders Group 3 --- healthy students. The level of nervous disorders increases with each academic year. Students with neurotic disorders are unable to regulate their regimens, which leads to deepening of asthenia (decreased central nervous system function, impaired ability to work, mental fatigue, memory impairment, etc.).

Students with neurotic disorders are unable to sleep well, and some are unable to use the weekend to relax. Neuroses also lead to a significant reduction in academic achievement. Among the students at risk are those who find it easier to communicate, improve their mood and drink alcohol in difficult

situations. (Abramova, GS Age psychology [Text]: textbook for students of universities / GS Abramova. - 5th ed. - M.: Academic Avenue: Alma Mater, 2005. - 702 p.)

The stress problem is complex and multifaceted. It is necessary to regulate stress in the educational process. The solution to this problem lies with the students themselves, their teachers, social educators and psychologists. Perhaps, in order to solve the problem, it is necessary to instill professional motivation in students, to add innovations to the educational process, such as a healthy lifestyle, training courses.

The intensity and intensity of modern life leads to the psychological impact of negative stress reactions and emotional tensions, which in turn lead to long-term stressful situations.

For the modern student, stress is perceived as the result of an endless process of struggle, such as a reaction to accumulated problems, a struggle with daily difficulties. These problems and difficulties for a high school student may include:

Insomnia ;

Practical and laboratory work not submitted or defended in time

Tasks not performed or not performed correctly ;

A large number of absentees from any subject ;

The course work is not ready for any point or the lesson project is not prepared ;

Incomplete mastery of the subject ;

Insufficient grade in a certain subject ;

Overloading the student with too much or too little work, as well as tasks that must be completed within a certain period of time ;

Conflict of roles. Such cases may occur if they do not meet the requirements of any informal group or formal organization (teacher). In such cases, the student may feel anxious and tense, because on the one hand he wants to be accepted by the group, on the other hand he wants to fulfill the requirements of the teacher;

Lack of interest in the subject or what is offered to the student;

Bad physical conditions (hall temperature, poor lighting, noise, etc.)

We can also add personal factors: the illness of family members, changes in the number of friends, conflicts with teammates and loved ones, travel, personal achievements, changes in financial situation, and other factors. There are many ways to deal with stress. In this study, we will focus on the work proposed by D. Myers. (Myers, D. Psychology / D. Myers; trans. From English IA Karpikov, VA Starovoitova. - 2nd ed. - Mn.: "Popurri", 2006. - 848 p.)

1. Keeping the situation under control for a certain period of time is no less important than managing stress. The feeling of being in control of the situation is perhaps the most important and fundamental issue needed to overcome stress.

2. Protecting from stress, you can also rely on the capabilities of the imagination. It is used for mental relaxation.

3. Short walk in the fresh air.

4. Visiting cultural and cultural-entertainment venues (theater, museum, exhibition, cinema, etc.)

5. Communicate with friends or other enjoyable campaigns.

6. The best medicine for stress is laughter. At this time, many muscles work, headaches are relieved, blood pressure drops, breathing and sleep are normalized. Antistress hormones also enter the bloodstream. During stress, the body usually secretes only the stress hormones adrenaline and cortisol.

7. Massage. You can also use self-massage.

8. Exercise (running, swimming, sports, etc.) Any exercise has an effect on stress hormones.

9. There are various exercises to deal with stress. This includes 3 types of exercises: relaxation (Euro-regulatory breathing exercises, muscle reaction, yoga) and concentration exercises. These exercises can be done anytime and anywhere, and it is recommended to use anti-stress breathing.

Thus, stress is an integral part of student life. The reaction to stress, such as the start of the working day, diet, mobility, quality of rest and sleep, interaction with the environment, is also part of a healthy lifestyle. It is up to the student to decide how to live, whether he is healthy, active or unhealthy and passive. The regularity and duration of his stress are also directly related to these factors.

Part 2. Research of psychological features of educational stress in students

2.1. Analysis of the results of the study of the psychological characteristics of educational stress in students.

The research part of this work was carried out at the Higher State University, Khanty-Mansiysk. The study involved first-year students, a group of 15 people studying pedagogy and psychology.

In the first phase of this work, we explored the main causes of stress during education, looked at how stress occurs, learned the basic methods for removing stress from students, and for this purpose YVSherbatikh has a test to determine stress during education. (Appendix 1)

The essence of this method is to ask students 7 questions. When answering the test in questions 1,3 and 5, the answers are evaluated on a 10-point scale, where 1 is considered a minimum and 10 points are considered a maximum. When answering questions 2, 4 and 6, the appropriate answer should be given. Question 7 is an open question, students should write their answers to this question.

The results of the study can be shown in the table below. (Table 1)

Table 1. Results of the study of the causes of stress in students

No	The cause of stress	Results, max = 10 b.
1	Lots of lessons	5.4
2	Fear of the future	4.9
3	The desire not to study or frustration in the chosen	4.7

	profession	
4	Unintelligible, boring textbooks	4.7
5	Inability to properly allocate limited financial resources.	4.5
6	Tough teachers	4.3
7	Problems in private life	4.1
8	Irregular nutrition	4.1
9	Not being able to manage your day properly	4.1
10	Shyness, timidity	3.6
11	Inappropriate seriousness in relation to education	3.2
12	Lack of textbooks	2.5
13	From parents _ _ _ far away life _ _	2.3
14	Conflict in the group	1.9
15	Problems of living with other students	1.5

Thus, as we have seen, the main reason for stress in students is the large workload and fear of the future. What worries students the least is living with other students and conflicts within the group. (It can be concluded that the group is kind.

The average exam excitement in the group is 8.3 on a 10-point scale. Students are more anxious than usual, apparently because they are "afraid of the future."

We can show the level of constant stress in the last 3 months as follows.

It seems that the level of constant stress in the last 3 school months has significantly decreased in 4 students. (26.7 percent) was assessed once in 5 students (33.3 percent). It did not decrease in 1 student (6.7 percent) and increased significantly in 3 students. (20 percent)

The characteristics of stress in students are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Stress in students

No	The emergence of stress	Results, max = 10 b.
1	urgency , constant lack of time	4.9
2	Poor concentration, distraction	4.7
3	Bad mood, depression	4.7
4	Bad sleep	4.4
5	Not being able to get rid of extraneous thoughts	4.2
6	Low ability to work, feeling tired	4.2
7	Resentment	4.1
8	Fear, excitement	4.1
9	Feelings of helplessness, inability to cope with problems	3.9
10	Headaches	3.9
11	Loss of confidence, loss of self-confidence	3.4

12	Disruption of social relations, communication problems	2.5
13	Rapid heartbeat, heart pain	2.3
14	Problems with the gastrointestinal tract	1.6
15	Deterioration of respiration	1.5
16	Muscle tension or swelling	1,2

In the group of students studied, stress manifests itself mainly on a psychological level, which manifests itself in students' reduced ability to work, poor sleep and lack of time. The biological symptoms of stress are low in the majority of students. Based on this, we can conclude that the majority of students are in good health.

Thus, the study shows that the most common symptoms of stress are heart palpitations (86.7%), headaches and other pains (73.4%), difficult breathing (53.4%), dry mouth (40%), muscle bloating (33.4%). . Examples of other symptoms include sleep disturbances and abdominal pain. The most common biological symptoms of stress are an increase in the number of heartbeats and various pains.

The results of the study of the main methods of stress management in students are shown in the table below.

Table 3. Methods of stress management

How to relieve stress	Number of students, in%
Sleep	100%
Communicate with friends and loved ones	80%
Walking in the fresh air	80%
Delicious food	73.4%
A break from work or study	60%
Support from parents	53.4%
Physical activity	46.7%
TV	26.7%
Sex	26.7%
Hobby	20%
Smoking	6.7%
Alcohol	6.7%
Drugs	-
Other : dancing , showering, changing activities, laughter therapy, self-indulgence	

The main method used to relieve stress is sleep. (100 percent of respondents use this method.) For the majority of surveyed students (80 percent), this method is to talk to friends or walk in the fresh air. This is a reliable way to relieve stress. More than half of those polled are seeking support from relatives and friends. Almost half of the students surveyed relieve stress through physical means, which is very useful for a person in such a situation. On the

plus side, alcohol and bad habits such as smoking are not used in the stress group we are researching.

In the second phase , we tested each student's stress tolerance, using the S. Cohen and G. Willison stress test. This test allows a person to measure how much he is resistant to stress. (In this case, the answers can be excellent, good, satisfactory, bad or very bad.)

This method uses 10 questions. When answering the test, students have to choose one of the standard answers given. (never, almost never, sometimes, often, quite often)

The results of the study are presented in the form of a table below. (Table 4)

Table 4. Assessment of stress tolerance

No	Name and surname.	Results, max = 40 b.	Evaluation
1	A. A.	12	Good
2	B. K.	27	Bad
3	VS	13	Good
4	Q. O.	21	Satisfactory
5	E. A.	14	Good
6	ZN	21	Satisfactory
7	K. Ī.	11	Good
8	K. A.	17	Satisfactory
9	M. V. _	13	Good
10	M. D. _	15	Satisfactory
11	M. L. _	17	Satisfactory
12	M. K.	16	Satisfactory
13	N. _ E.	18	Satisfactory
14	V. A.	16	Satisfactory
15	S. M.	18	Satisfactory
	Average indicator for the group	16.6	Satisfactory

It can be seen from this table that 33.4% of students received a “good” grade, 60% received a “ Satisfactory” grade and 6.6 % received a “bad” grade. Also at the time of testing, stress tolerance was 16.6 out of 40. This figure can also be considered satisfactory.

Analyzing all the results obtained, it is possible to come to the following conclusions ::

The main causes of stress among the students of the group we are researching are the fear of the great workload.

Stress in this group is mainly psychological, which leads to a decrease in students' ability to work, poor sleep and lack of time.

The biological effects of stress on most students are negligible. Based on this, we can say that the majority of students are healthy.

The main tools used by students to deal with stress during sleep are sleep (100 percent of respondents), as well as communication with loved ones and walking in the fresh air (80 percent), delicious food (73.4 percent), parental support (53 percent).

Among the students, the most common symptoms of stress were rapid heartbeat (86.7 percent), headaches and other pains (73.4 percent), difficulty breathing (53.4 percent), dry mouth (40 percent), bloating and muscle tension (33.4 percent).

The stress tolerance of the students in the study group was 16.6 on a 40-point scale, which is a satisfactory result on that table. Based on this, we can conclude that the stress tolerance is adequate and the stress tolerance of the students in the group is satisfactory.

Thus, our hypothesis that the heavy workload during the educational process in higher education institutions is one of the main reasons for the role of stress in students has proved true.

2.2 Recommended recommendations for relieving stress and anxiety in students.

Based on the studied scientific materials and obtained results, we offer the following recommendations.

For university students:

1. Develop a system of priorities in your work, perform daily tasks in a certain sequence.
2. Be able to say "no" when you see that you can no longer work after reaching a certain level.
3. Build a particularly effective and trusting relationship with your teachers.
4. Don't agree with anyone who makes conflicting demands.
5. If the task and its assessment standards are not clear, inform your teacher so that you can facilitate future tasks.
6. Set a time and day to move from work to productive rest. As for other factors related to the reduction of the likelihood of stress, adherence to a diet, staying in good shape through physical exercise, and other such factors are very useful.

With regard to stressful events and situations, the recommendations for overcoming the negative effects of such situations on the body are as follows:

1. Gather enough information about the approach of a stressful situation.
2. Development of warning methods for specific life threats, their prevention.
3. On the eve of a stressful event, you should avoid making hasty decisions, as events may take place in a completely different direction than you can imagine.
4. It is important to remember that most of the stressful situations can be solved by oneself without running to the help of others.
5. Be proactive in stressful situations. An active lifestyle creates a background of protection against stress in the body, helps to improve adaptation.

6. It is important to understand and accept that serious change is an integral part of life.

7. It is important to remember that people who are able to use relaxation techniques are more likely to emerge from stressful life events.

Relaxation plays a role as the most effective protection against stress. According to G. Selyen's theory, the automatic alarm reaction consists of 3 successive stages: impulse, stress and adaptation. Thus, if a person wants to focus his efforts on maintaining his health, he must respond to the stress impulse with relaxation.

Breathing can be difficult and difficult in situations of physical tension or stress. A person can consciously control his breathing and use it to calm down and relieve tension, thus eliminating both the tension of the muscles and the psyche, and thus controlling breathing becomes a means of combating stress, relaxation and concentration.

A personal stress self-analysis can also be done through a "stress diary" to analyze and detect your body's reactions to stressful situations. When using this method, it is necessary to note in what cases and when symptoms of stress are detected within a few weeks. Diary entries allow you to identify what events and situations are causing the stress. Constantly repetitive situations can be a major cause of stress.

First aid methods during acute stress. When you are suddenly in a state of stress, you need to mobilize all your willpower and command yourself to stop immediately, this method can prevent the development of acute stress. Effective self-help measures need to be found to cope with acute stress and calm down. The following methods can be used during acute stress to recover immediately in a critical situation:

1. Anti-stress breathing;
2. Relaxation;
3. Rational perception of the environment;
4. Change of circumstances;
5. Do not engage in any outside (distracting) work.

This plays a distracting role in stressful situations. It is possible to get rid of internal tension through this method.

6. Local concentration (helps to eliminate the internal dialogue caused by stress.)

Stress is inevitable, you need to know about it and always remember. At the same time, it is possible to anticipate stress, prepare for it and deal with it effectively.

Conclusion

Stress has become extremely common for the modern student. Stress is a reaction to accumulated problems in an endless process of coping with daily challenges. Stress is the result of work or organizational work, events that occur in a person's personal life. Stress in student life involves daily difficulties, while we must take into account the characteristics of the educational process in higher education and the direct and indirect effects that lead to changes in mental and somatic functions that affect human emotions. Thus, stress has

become an integral part of every student's life. Reaction to stress is part of a lifestyle such as the start of a daily work day, diet, activity, quality of sleep and rest. It is up to the student to decide what his / her lifestyle will be like - healthy, active or unhealthy and passive. Based on this, we can say how often and for how long he will be in a state of stress.

In our research, we tried to study the stressful situations of students in the educational process. At the same time, we found that the main reasons for stress in students are the large workload from different subjects. All this leads to haste and constant lack of time. Students usually regain their strength through sound sleep and communication with friends and relatives.

Thus, our hypothesis that the heavy workload during the educational process in higher education institutions is one of the main reasons for the role of stress in students has proved true.

References

1. Abramova, GS Age psychology [Text]: textbook. student allowance. universities / G.S. Abramova. - 5th ed. - M.: Academic Avenue: Alma Mater, 2005. - 702 p.
2. Andreeva, D.A. About the concept of adaptation. Research of adaptation of students to the conditions of teaching in the university // Man and society [Text]: Uch. notes XIII. - L.: LGU, 1973. - 69 p.
3. Бодров, В.А. Information stress [Text]. М.: PER SE, 2004. - 382 p.
4. Бодров, В.А. Psychological stress: development and overcoming [Text] - М.: PER SE, 2006. - 528 p.
5. Gorizontov, P.D. Stress [Text]: BME, 1963. - 628 p.
6. Grimak, L.P. Reserves of human psyche [Text]: М.: Politizdat, 1987. - 286 p.
7. Gubachev, Yu.M., Ievlev, BV, Karvasarsky, B.D. and others. Emotional stress in the conditions of norms and pathology [Text] :. L.: Medicine, 1996. - 224 p.
8. Игумнов, С.А. Stress management: modern psychological and medical approaches [Text] :. - SPb.: Rech, 2007. - 217 p.
9. Изард, К. Human emotions [Text] :. М.: Izd-vo Mosk. un-ta, 1980. - 440 p.
10. Космолинский, Ф.П. Emotional stress at work in extreme conditions [Text] :. М.: Medicine, 1976. - 190 p.
11. Мухина, В. С. Age psychology: the phenomenon of development, childhood, procreation [Text]: Textbook for students. universities. - 4th ed., Stereotype./V.S. Mukhina - М.: Publishing House "Academy", 1999. - 456 p.
12. Lazarus, R.S. Individual sensitivity and resilience to psychological stress // Psychological factors in work and protection of health [Text] :. М. - Geneva, 1989. - 121-126 p.
13. Лазарус, Р. Theory of stress and psychophysiological research // Emotional stress [Text]: Ed. L. Levi. L.: Medicine, 1970. - 178-208.

14. Myers, D. Psychology / D. Myers; пер. с англ. I.A. Карпиков, В.А. Starovoitova. - 2nd ed. - Мн. : "Popurri", 2006. - 848 p.
15. Мирева, И.Ю. Stress management course [Text] :. Moscow: ICC "March", 2004. - p.288
16. Селъе, Г. At the level of the whole organism [Text] :. М. : Nauka, 1972. - 122 p.
17. Селъе, Г. Stress without distress [Text] :. М. : Progress, 1979. - 124 p.
18. Smith, T. D.J. Professional stress // Human factor / Ed. Г. Salvendi. М. : Mir, 1991. - 356-392 p .
19. Suvorova, VV Psychophysiology of stress [Text] :. М. : Pedagogika, 1985. - 208 p.
20. Faustov, AS, Shcherbatykh, Yu.V. Correction of the level of examination stress in students as a factor in improving their health // Health of the Russian Federation. 2001, №4, pp. 38-39.
21. Shcherbatykh, Yu.V. Psychology of stress and methods of correction [Text] :. St. Petersburg: Peter, 2006. - 256 p.
22. Shcherbatykh, Yu.V. Influence of indicators of the highest nervous activity of students on the nature of the examination of examination stress // Journal of the VND. Pavlova, 2000, №6, 959-965 p.
23. Shcherbatykh Yu.V. Application of methods of self-regulation and neurolinguistic programming to reduce the level of stress in students // Prevention of violations in the student environment. Voronezh: VGPU, 2003. - 105-107 p.
24. URL : [http : // www . no - stress . ru / testy / stress . html](http://www.no-stress.ru/testy/stress.html) - Test for academic stress. Developed by Yu.V. Shcherbatykh.
25. URL : [http : // www . gurutestov . ru](http://www.gurutestov.ru) - Self-esteem test of stress resistance S. Cohen and G. Willianson.